
Plant viral nanoparticles can be used in biological systems for loading and transporting cargo

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Abstract: PVNPs (plant viral nanoparticles) can be used in biological systems for loading and transporting cargo. Small dimensions, high avidity target binding due to numerous targeting ligands per PVNP, configurable and modular physicochemical characteristics, image multiplexing capacity and concomitant capability for massive payload distribution in diverse situations are all aspects contributing to their use. Highly useful materials can be created for future purposes due to physicochemical and genetic alterations. PVNPs can be tailored and loaded for specific applications using physical techniques allowing cargo to be loaded through physical interactions; chemical techniques linking cargo or targeting ligands to external or internal capsid; genetic techniques allowing precise and repeatable manipulations; and combined techniques combining multiple loading methods to generate more options. To optimize loading, selecting the most effective way to match the appropriate cargo is important. Loading and releasing cargo from the particles are essential elements of PVNP-based delivery systems, and both operations are often connected. PVNP's characteristics, the cargo to be loaded, and the rationale for producing the unique nanoparticle all impact whether the techniques are optimal for a given system.

1. Introduction

For nanoscience and nanotechnology, a variety of viral-based nanomaterial vehicles have been used. They may convey materials (or "cargo"), such as contrast agents or medicines, and they can be tailored to deliver materials to specific tissues (Hu, Masarapu, et al., 2019). Viruses infecting all living things are natural nanostructures that have developed to allow them to spread across and among the creatures they infect (Jeevanandam, Barhoum, Chan, Dufresne, & Danquah, 2018). Viruses have a nucleic acid genome and a protein coat called the capsid, which is formed by coat proteins self-assembling (CPs). Viral capsids serve as an engineering scaffold that can be changed by physicochemical alterations and/or manipulation of the capsid's nucleic acid template. The use of viruses as adaptable nanostructures for molecular trapping and material production began with the disassembly of the virus and the replacement of the genome with synthetic polymers (Douglas & Young, 1998). Viral-like particles (VLPs), or empty capsids, are also important reagents for nanoengineering.

Viruses are unusual reagents for nanoengineering because of their general features such as biodegradability, biocompatibility, monodispersed size, and shape, as well as their size range in the standard "nanoparticle" size range of 10–200 nm. Plant viruses are also non-pathogenic to mammals and are generally considered safe for use in nanomedicine (Balique, Lecoq, Raoult, & Colson, 2015; Blandino et al., 2015; Eiben et al., 2019; Masarapu et al., 2017). Plant viruses have been widely exploited as nanoscale structures for a variety of purposes (Steele et al., 2017). Viruses are built to be delivery vehicles from the start. Their form and

function as carriers of nucleic acids enable them to bundle and deliver a variety of payloads to specified biological areas (Cheng et al., 2012).

PVNPs (plant viral nanoparticles) may transport cargo both inside and outside the capsid. Cargo can either pass through the capsid to reach the interior or be incorporated into the capsid cavity during capsid construction, a process known as encapsidation. Chemically addressable amino acids can be used to attach cargo to fixed places on the exterior of the capsid. Both procedures are complimentary, and genetic modification of the virus might be used to improve either (Aniagyei, DuFort, Kao, & Dragnea, 2008). The ideas and possibilities for cargo loading of plant PVNPs are discussed in this article. The focus will be on theoretical and experimental insights into physical, chemical, and genetic principles and tactics for capsid loading and modification, as well as the sorts of payloads currently of interest.

2. Nanoparticles of plant virus

PVNPs include both infectious viruses (virions) and VLPs that are not infectious to any plant for various reasons. A protective proteinaceous shell (capsid) surrounds the nucleic acid genome, which may or may not be coated by an outer membrane containing lipids (enveloped viruses). Enveloped viruses are delicate and susceptible to denaturation and dehydration (Grein, Weidner, & Czermak, 2017). Plant viruses are seldom enclosed, making them more stable outside of the host and allowing direct access to the capsid, which is often restricted by the envelope (Aniagyei et al., 2008). Plant viruses come in a range of sizes, with elongated helical forms and approximately spherical icosahedral forms being the most common (Röder, Dickmeis, & Commandeur, 2019). The viral genome regulates viral features such as form, size, monodispersity, permeability to smaller molecules, self-assembly, pH and temperature stability, and host range (Jeevanandam et al., 2018). Plant viruses are not pathogenic to animals and are therefore safe to use in human and animal treatment; however, concerns about plant pathogen distribution must be addressed. Plant virus capsids are a unique class of bio-inspired nanomaterials that can be used in medicinal and non-medical applications (Aniagyei et al., 2008; L. Schoonen, Maassen, Nolte, & van Hest, 2017; Y. Zhang, Ardejani, & Orner, 2016). The most commonly used platforms are icosahedral (e.g., cowpea mosaic virus, CPMV), helical rigid (e.g., tobacco mosaic virus, TMV), and helical flexible (e.g., potato virus X, PVX), and some PVNP and their applications have recently been reviewed (A. A. Aljabali, Berardi, & Evans, 2018; Röder et al., 2019).

Capsids are self-assembling macromolecular structures that generate homogeneous hollow containers with active interior and exterior surfaces. Yuste-Calvo, González-Gamboa, Pacios, Sánchez, & Ponz (2019) found that these surfaces had large concentrations of electrostatic charges and chemically accessible groups. Furthermore, under certain environmental conditions (e.g., pH), many PVNPs can be dissociated and reassembled *in vitro* to create structures with variable open or closed states, allowing them to be used for packaging various cargoes (Daz-Valle, Garca-Salcedo, Chávez-Calvillo, Silva-Rosales, & Carrillo-Tripp, 2015; Lam, Lin, & Steinmetz, 2018; Perlman). As a result, physicochemical treatment of PVNPs can alter physical properties such as electrostatic, hydrophobic, and steric parameters, allowing disassembly for nucleic acid removal and creation of noninfectious empty VLPs, as well as reassembly for cargo encapsulation (Garmann, Comas-Garcia, Knobler, & Gelbart, 2015).

2.1 PVNP production

PVNP may be produced efficiently by mechanical inoculation with homogenized tissue from infected leaves or virions, then purified utilizing biochemical procedures (Dijkstra & de Jager,

2012). After inoculating plants, some PVNPs can be recovered in gram quantities from 1 kg of infected leaf material in 2–4 weeks (Evans, 2008). VLPs can be created using molecular biology procedures in which the genes encoding the viral capsid proteins are transcribed in a heterologous expression system, or by disassembly and reassembly without the use of nucleic acids (Marsian & Lomonosoff, 2016).

3. Cargo loading of nanoparticles of plant virus.

PVNPs may contain active surfaces that allow cargo to be attached to the viral exterior, interior, and interface between neighboring CPs. In vitro and in vivo procedures can be used to attach cargo molecules using physicochemical and protein engineering techniques (Koudelka & Manchester, 2010). The tactics accessible for a certain PVNP system are determined by the PV structure, the cargo environment that the NP is projected to meet, and the loading procedures that are accessible for that PVNP. Optimizing cargo loading necessitates the use of appropriate procedures. Interactions of cargo with nonmodified PVNP, structural alterations in the PVNP, and engineering alterations to generate genetically modified PVNP are all common ways of cargo loading. As a result, cargo loading tactics can be classified as genetic or nongenetic, as outlined in the following sections. Nongenetic techniques are applicable to all nanomaterials, but genetic techniques are exclusively applicable to proteinaceous-based nanomaterials (Bhaskar & Lim, 2017). These methods allow cargos of interest to be fused to or contained inside PVNPs' internal, exterior, and intersubunit interfaces (Vardhan et al., 2019).

3.1 Cargo loading techniques that aren't genetic

Viruses are nanocontainers that build themselves through electrostatic, ionic, and hydrophobic interactions between capsid proteins and the DNA (Chevreuil et al., 2018). Physicochemical interactions are important factors that influence cargo loading efficiency, affinity, and release rates (Glidden et al., 2017). PVNPs that change in reaction to environmental circumstances can aid in the loading and unloading of fake cargos (Cheng et al., 2012; Pokorski & Steinmetz, 2010; Thong, Biabanikhankahdani, Ho, Alitheen, & Tan, 2019). Some PVNPs have selective or nonselective holes that may be opened and employed for entrapping under the impact of ambient circumstances (pH, salt, particular ions) (Cao et al., 2014). Adhesion chemistry allows for the encapsulation and accumulation of additional structures inside or on the surface of the capsid, such as gold NPs (Arcangeli et al., 2014; Cao et al., 2014; Miao, Johnson, & Ortoleva, 2010; Prasuhn, Yeh, Obenaus, Manchester, & Finn, 2007; Wen et al., 2012; Wu, Yang, & Shin, 2013; Zeng et al., 2013). Nongenetic PVNP cargo loading can be accomplished in a number of ways, as mentioned below.

3.1.1 Method of incubation

Without employing covalent chemical processes, noncovalent interactions of the cargo with PVNPs can be achieved by hydrophobic/hydrophilic, electrostatic/charge, and hydrogen bonding interactions, resulting in PVNPcargo complexes (D. H. Le, Lee, Shukla, Commandeur, & Steinmetz, 2017). A large number of goods can be loaded by using opposing charges. The residual charge of amino acids determines the quantity and kind of surface charge inside or outside the capsid, and these charges impact cargo loading.

3.1.2 Method of infusion

Some capsid subunits have pores that are either constantly open or alternate between open and closed states (Mateu, 2013). They allow the payload to diffuse into the inside of the capsid.

Changing environmental factors can have an impact on capsid structure, facilitating cargo dispersion and retention (Cao et al., 2014; Miao et al., 2010).

The infusion procedure is extremely simple.

Through pores, certain PVNPs allow cargo to collect within the capsid interior (Mateu, 2013). The electrostatic sponge feature of the genome or contact with certain amino acids on the inner surface can keep cargo in place (Yildiz, Lee, Chen, Shukla, & Steinmetz, 2013; Zeng et al., 2013). Some substances, such as dye molecules, ions (Gd, La), hydrophilic bioactive molecules, photosensitizers (PS), medicines, and other positively charged molecules, have been proven to do so. When opposed to negatively charged cargoes, positive and neutral charge cargoes may have a higher loading yield (Loo, Guenther, Lommel, & Franzen, 2008). The cargo's hydrophobic groups, affinity for nucleic acids, and large molecular weight can all help to prevent leaching during dilution. This technique has been described in PVNPs such as CPMV (Wen, Le, Zhou, Steinmetz, & Popkin, 2015), Cucumber mosaic virus (Zeng et al., 2013), and PhMV VLP (Wen, Le, Zhou, Steinmetz, & Popkin, 2015). (Masarapu et al., 2017).

Diffusion gating mechanism

The opening and shutting of gated pores in the capsid is involved in this action. When pores are open, diffusion occurs, and when pores are closed, retention occurs. Electrostatic interactions, buffer conditions, pH, and/or metal ion concentration influence these gating changes (Cao et al., 2015; Mateu, 2013). Understanding and modifying the factors that affect the pore state allows cargo loading and release rates to be controlled. Artichoke mottled crinkle virus (Arcangeli et al., 2014), cowpea chlorotic mottle virus (CCMV) (Miao et al., 2010), red clover necrotic mosaic virus (RCNMV) (Loo et al., 2008), and Johnson grass chlorotic stripe mosaic virus are among the PVNPs for which this approach has been published (Alemzadeh et al., 2019). For loading cargo into numerous PVNPs, infusion techniques and related gated diffusion have been disclosed.

3.1.3 Method of disassembly and reassembly

The self-assembly of viral capsid components around a virus's native genome is widely known (Aniagyei et al., 2008; Mateu, 2013). In vitro, changing the buffering conditions (pH and ionic strength) can cause the capsid to breakdown and the genome to be released. Many viral capsids will rebuild and enclose a new payload under the correct conditions (Steele et al., 2017). Cargo size, surface charge, electrostatic interactions, hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity, critical assembly concentrations of CP, and specific binding interactions that occur during nanoassembly are all factors that impact cargo encapsulation (Koudelka, Pitek, Manchester, & Steinmetz, 2015; Wen & Steinmetz, 2016).

Electrostatic interactions between positively charged capsid protein groups and negatively charged cargo are required in many circumstances for reassembly. In order to assist reassembly, this method needs a sufficient negative net charge for the core cargo (Mieloch et al., 2018). Positively charged cargos can be loaded into a capsid that requires a negatively charged cargo to reassemble by combining them with another negatively charged cargo to provide enough net negative charge to accelerate capsid assembly (Ren, Wong, & Lim, 2007). Another method is to use an artificial origin-of-assembly site (OAS) on metallic, magnetic, or semiconductor nanoparticles to test the assembly. The creation of the protein/nucleic acid cage structure in certain plant viruses begins with the CP's particular identification of a viral genome sequence. OAS is a sequence that promotes self-assembly by initiating CP monomer binding and promoting self-assembly. On a cargo of interest, an artificial OAS can therefore

be formed. In vitro self-assembly around OAS-conjugated cargos happens when they are combined with CP monomers (Loo et al., 2007). If a cargo lacks the requisite negative charge for self-assembly, it can be coated with negatively charged polymers or polyprotic acid in an analogous templated assembly process (Chen et al., 2006). The protein is generated in an expression system, purified, and then combined with CP subunits in vitro under optimal circumstances to encapsulate protein cargos (Sharma et al., 2017).

3.1.4 Method of constrained synthesis

The diverse surface chemistry and high charge density on the inner and outer surfaces of many capsids can function as a nanoreactor for cargo production and precursor material loading. Precursor materials may diffuse into the internal cavity or be deposited on the surface of constructed PVNPs, where the material nucleates and crystallizes, resulting in the formation of inorganic nanocrystals. The reduction of Au^{3+} to Au^0 and the production of nanoparticles were caused by electron transfer from surface tyrosine residues and reduction of AuCl_4 via a combined deprotonation/electron transfer process (Slocik et al., 2005). From precursor anions inside the capsid, nanoparticles containing salts of polyoxometalate (Douglas & Young, 1998), titanium oxide (TiO_2), and Prussian blue (A. de la Escosura et al., 2008; Klem, Young, & Douglas, 2008) have been made. The Squash leaf curl China virus was recently used to create metallic-hybrid PVNPs. To make this reagent for bio-semiconductor applications, researchers employed this virus in a restricted synthesis using gold chloride (HAuCl_4) and silver nitrate (AgNO_3), as well as sunshine (to promote photocatalytic reduction) (Thangavelu, Ganapathy, Ramasamy, & Krishnan, 2018).

3.1.5 Method of biomineralization

The process by which living organisms make minerals and biotemplates for nucleation and aggregation of those minerals for biological functions such as forming protective shells is known as bio-mineralization (Bedwell et al., 2015). PVNP surfaces can be used as biotemplates to make controlled inorganic mineral nanomaterials. Electrostatic interaction, affinity tags, and seed formation inside capsids or electroless deposition can attract and trap mineral cargo on the inner and outer surface of capsids (W. Zhang et al., 2017). (Balci et al., 2012; Knez et al., 2003; Niehl et al., 2016; Reichhardt et al., 2011; Tsukamoto, Muraoka, Seki, Tabata, & Yamashita, 2007; K. Zhou, Li, Dai, Meng, & Wang, 2013; Z. Zhou, Bedwell, Li, Prevelige, & Gupta, 2014). Mineralization of para tungstate, decavanadate, and $-\text{TiO}_2$ NPs in CCMV via a gating mechanism, iron oxide and Co NPs in CPMV by simple infusion, and inorganic seeds in TMV's central channel are all examples (Jaafar et al., 2014).

3.1.6 Methods of bioconjugation

Bio-conjugation is the process of joining two or more biomolecules together to form a new hybrid material or to insert a functional group into the biomolecule. Capsid proteins' amino acid side chains or connected carbohydrates serve as bioconjugation targets on PVNPs (Steinmetz & Manchester, 2011). PVNPs have been bioconjugated to load medicinal and theranostic compounds, as well as target ligands and conducting materials for new nanoelectronic and light-harvesting devices.

Surface groupings that can be addressed

For modification and bioconjugation chemistries, functional accessible groups on reactive amino acid side chains such as an amine (Lys), carboxylate (Asp, Glu), thiol (Cys), and aromatic groups (Tyr, Trp) can be used (deGruyter, Malins, & Baran, 2017; Mohan & Weiss, 2016). The following are the principles of this method: (a) structure analysis reveals exposed

amino acids on capsid surfaces, (b) pH activation of functional addressable groups of amino acid side chains, isothiocyanate-mediated coupling, N-hydroxysuccinimide esters (NHS) (Wen et al., 2012), 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) (Esfandi For example, a thorough examination of the structure of the tobacco mild green mosaic virus (TMGMV) revealed solvent-exposed Tyr2, Glu145, and Asp66 on the exterior surface, as well as Glu95 and Glu106 on the interior surface, and established the chemical addressability of these residues as a carrier for anthelmintic drugs like crystal violet (Chariou & Steinmetz, 2017). Bioorthogonal processes (click reaction and oxime ligation) (Chakraborty, 2018), which need low concentrations of the reagent or ligand and so have reduced costs, are practical and effective bioconjugation procedures. For bioconjugation of PS on CPMV (Wen et al., 2016), Alexa Fluor 647 on PVX, doxorubicin (DOX) on TMV (Finbloom et al., 2016), and Alexa Fluor 488 and Cy5.5 on Sesbania mosaic virus (SeMV), these procedures have been frequently employed (Vardhan et al., 2019).

Method based on enzymes

This method relies on an enzyme that can directly connect the cargo (typically a peptide) to the PVNP. Enzymes are capable of catalyzing the attachment of certain amino-acid sequences from one protein to another protein, peptide, or smaller molecule. Because it allows the connection of long amino acid sequences to the already assembled capsid, this method can overcome problems in the assembly of genetically engineered chimeric capsid proteins, such as generating antigen-VLP conjugates, as reported for PapMV (Brune et al., 2016; Reddington & Howarth, 2015; Thérien et al., 2017).

3.2 Cargo loading techniques based on genetics

PVNPs have a significant advantage over other synthetic materials in that they can be genetically modified to change their structural structure. Because many plant viruses have tiny, sequenced genomes, genetically stable PVNP variants may be easily generated at little cost (Lebel, Chartrand, Leclerc, & Lamarre, 2015).

Loading of expressions

Cargo packing in PVNPs can be accomplished by genetically-allowed directed-loading of cargo during PVNP formation *in vivo*, allowing for cargo spatial control. PVNPs can be used to make complicated catalytic biomaterials using this method (Patterson et al., 2012; Patterson et al., 2013; Sharma et al., 2017). Heterogeneous expression methods express the cargo and CP concurrently, followed by self-assembly *in vitro* or *in vivo*. By adding cargo-encoding sequence into genes encoding CP (N-, C-terminal, and internal fusions of cargos), genetic approaches allow cargo (AA, tags, epitopes) to be introduced into VLP coats (Balke & Zeltins, 2019; Bendahmane et al., 1999).

This popular method of genetically engineering PVNPs involves making amino acid alterations, deletions, or insertions in a gene encoding a CP, then expressing the modified gene in a system that allows capsid assembly. The amount and kinds of sites accessible for bio-conjugation of materials to the exterior or inside of the capsid may be controlled by genetic modification of CP, as well as the overall physicochemical features like electrostatic interactions (Badri Narayanan & Soo Han, 2017). As a result, several copies of the appropriate protein cargo are displayed on or in the PVNP by the capsid (Koudelka et al., 2015; Lebel et al., 2015; Vitti et al., 2010). Incorporating cysteine or lysine as chemically addressable groups on CP is one type of use (Steele et al., 2017). The insertion of a hexahistidine tag enables the purification, immobilization, and assembly of array structures, and it

was used with TMV (Bruckman et al., 2011). On CPMV, genetic deletion of lysine decreased the number of addressable sites (Chatterji, Ochoa, Ueno, Lin, & Johnson, 2005) or changed the surface charge of the capsid (Chatterji, Ochoa, Ueno, Lin, & Johnson, 2005). (Douglas et al., 2002).

Vaccines, such as the ectodomain of the influenza A M2 protein (Brennan et al., 1999), outer membrane protein F of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gilleland et al., 2000), and fibronectin-binding protein B of *Staphylococcus aureus* (Brennan et al., 1999), (Meshcheryakova et al., 2009). Glycoprotein 41 of HIV-1 (Marusic et al., 2001) and the hepatitis C virus hypervariable region I peptide R9 have been expressed on the surface of PVX (Uhde-Holzem, Schlösser, Viazov, Fischer, & Commandeur, 2010), and infectious bursal disease virus VP2 epitopes have been expressed on *Physalis mottle virus* (PhMV) CP (Sahithi et al., 2019).

The cargo and its inclusion in CP must not disturb capsid formation, which is the fundamental restriction of genetic engineering for cargo loading. The inclusion of significant regions of other proteins might clearly affect the capsid's assembly and stability. Despite this drawback, one of the most successful loading strategies for PVNPs is genetic engineering.

3.2.1 Loading of coexpression

The simultaneous expression of CP and proteinous cargo from the same or distinct vectors using an expression system to make the proteins is known as co-expression loading (Dashti, Abidin, & Sainsbury, 2018). The 24K proteinase was encapsulated within the CPMV capsid using this approach (Sainsbury & Lomonosoff, 2014).

Cargos and applications for loading in PVNPS

PVNPs are appealing *in vivo* tools because of their ability to deliver a variety of cargos *in vivo* with little adverse effects (Kernan, Wen, Pitek, & Steinmetz, 2017; Yildiz, Shukla, & Steinmetz, 2011). Biocompatibility, biodegradability, and targetability are also desirable features for *in vivo* use. This promise is strengthened by the wide range of cargo loads that can be used for therapeutics, therapy, and tissue engineering.

4.1 Cargoes for PVNP loading

4.1.1 Protein-based cargo loading

PVNPs are potential nanotechnologies for loading proteins and enzymes for improved catalytic activity, temperature, pH, and protease resistance, as well as for generating multireaction nanoreactors (Glasgow, Capehart, Francis, & Tullman-Ercek, 2012; Wilkerson, Yang, Funk, Stanley, & Bundy, 2018). Horseradish peroxidase, glucose oxidase, teal, and green fluorescent proteins (GFPs), CYPBM3 (a cytochrome P450 variation), and a bacterial CYP variation have all been documented to be loaded by PVNPs (Brasch et al., 2017; de Ruiten, Putri, & Cornelissen, 2018; Minten, Hendriks, Nolte, & Cornelissen, 2009; Rurup et al., 2014; L. Schoonen, Nolte, & van Hest, 2016). For loading conjugated *Candida antarctica* lipase B, amino groups on the exterior surface of the turnip mosaic virus were employed (Cuenca et al., 2016).

PVNP-based enzyme delivery systems can change tamoxifen, a chemotherapeutic pro-drug, and resveratrol, a developing pro-drug (Sanchez-Sanchez et al., 2014). Optical imaging may be achieved by conjugating TMV with streptokinase (Brasch et al., 2011), GFP, and mCherry on PVX (S. Shukla et al., 2014). Immunogenic epitopes like CH401 can be fused or conjugated to CCMV, SeMV, and CPMV capsids to activate immune responses against

cancer (Cai, Shukla, Wang, Masarapu, & Steinmetz, 2019). For loading these components, genetic and bioconjugation approaches are commonly utilized.

4.1.2 Smaller nanoparticles are loaded into PVNPs.

PVNPs may load and transport both natural and synthetic nanoparticles. Because the capsid cavity in wild-type virions is about 17 nm, bioconjugating small gold nanoparticles (5 nm) on the outer surface of CPMV (Blum et al., 2004) and encapsulating larger single particles (>8 nm) through self-assembly of Brome mosaic virus (BMV), or RCNMV (Loo et al., 2007) demonstrates the importance of size in loading Active PVNPs for imaging were created by encapsulating and functionalizing cubic iron oxide NPs in BMV (Huang et al., 2011) and fluorescent polyanionic semiconducting polymer in CCMV (Ng, Chan, Lin, & Tolbert, 2011). Chemical and genetic manipulation of CCMV capsids with nanoassembly can be applied to the encapsulation of inorganic nanoparticles such as quantum dots (Tagit et al., 2017) or Prussian blue nanoparticles (Wu, Yang, & Shin, 2014) to produce functional nanohybrid materials with tunable sizes and functions. To reduce nitrogen, CCMV bearing gold nanoparticles was utilized (the reduction sequence is nitrogen hydroxylamine amine) (A. Liu, Traulsen, & Cornelissen, 2016).

4.1.3 Nucleic acid loading

The intensity of the CP–CP and CP–genome contacts, pH, the absolute quantity of nucleic acid, and the relative concentration of CP and nucleic acid polymer all influence the role of the nucleic acid polymer as a scaffold and active component in capsid formation (Cadena-Nava et al., 2012; Comas-Garcia et al., 2014). The Carnation Italian ring spot virus capsid component was genetically modified to encapsulate siRNA for effective cytoplasmic delivery and serum stability (Choi, Choi, Jeon, Kim, & Ahn, 2011). CCMV CP has recently been utilized to encapsulate Sindbis virus heterologous RNA (Lam & Steinmetz, 2018), siRNAs (Lam & Steinmetz, 2019), and mRNA-EGFP (Villagrana-Escareo et al., 2019) for delivery into mammalian cells for nucleic acid therapies, gene knockdown, and as reporter genes. CCMV can transmit a self-amplifying ("replicon") mRNA to activate dendritic cells as a vaccine/gene delivery platform (Biddlecome et al., 2019).

4.1.4 Dosage loading

PVNPs can be used as a drug delivery nanoplatform because of their homogeneous size and structure, as well as their ability to be modified chemically and genetically to load medicines and incorporate targeting moieties (Wong & Ren, 2018). phenanthriplatin (A. E. Czapar et al., 2016; Vernekar et al., 2018), DOX (Alemzadeh et al., 2019; Aljabali et al., 2013; Lockney et al., 2011; Tian et al., 2016), cisplatin (Franke, Czapar, Patel, & Steinmetz, 2018; X. Liu (Wen, Le, et al., 2015). Ren et al. (2007) formed polynucleotides and polyacids as scaffolding for drug loading into capsids. A new treatment for diabetic atherosclerosis has been created using a noncovalent loading of trivalent chromium (CrCl₃) in CPMV (Ganguly et al., 2016). All of the nongenetic loading strategies mentioned have the ability to load pharmaceuticals into PVNPs, and the best strategy relies on the virus, drug, and application features.

4.1.5 Pesticide loading

PVNP can potentially be utilized to enhance pesticide delivery for agricultural parasite control. TMGMV is now loaded with antihelminthic medicines (crystal violet) via chemically accessible capsid groups, improving mobility and soil penetration (Chariou & Steinmetz, 2017). To target parasitic nematodes, a PVNP-delivery system using RCNMV for Abamectin, a biological insecticide, was employed (Cao et al., 2015). When it comes to defending plant

roots from nematodes, these nanoplatfoms are typically more effective than free insecticides (P. L. Chariou, Doga, et al., 2019; P. L. Chariou, Wang, et al., 2019).

4.1.6 Optical imaging agents are loaded.

Many imaging methods use contrast chemicals, which may be encapsulated in nanomaterials, and imaging is a critical duty in medicine (Smith & Gambhir, 2017). PVNPs enhance imaging by providing large imaging payloads, resulting in increased sensitivity, multiplexing capacity, and design adaptability (S. Shukla & Steinmetz, 2015). Optical imaging agents such as indocyanine green, an NIR fluorophore (Jung, Rao, & Anvari, 2011), fluorescent Oregon Green 488, Alexa Fluor 647 (Steinmetz et al., 2009), Alexa Fluor 555 (Lewis et al., 2006), iLOV fluorescent (Roder, Dickmeis, Fischer, & Commandeur, 2018), GFP, mCherry (S. For two-photon microscopy, BF3Dye coupling to TMV is a suitable nanocarrier (Niehl et al., 2016). PhMV particles containing the fluorescent dye Cy5.5 and paramagnetic gadolinium (Gd) complexes were created to use near-infrared fluorescence and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to monitor a human prostate tumor model (Hu, Masarapu, et al., 2019). CPMV has been used for cell imaging and tumor targeting using variable amounts of a VEGFR-1 ligand and a fluorescent PEGylated peptide (Brunel et al., 2010).

4.1.7 PS Loading

PS, a light source, and oxygen are required for photodynamic treatment (PDT). Low solubility and buildup are key drawbacks of using PSs, but PVNPs containing the photosensitizing chemical can solve these issues. When compared to free PS, loading a cationic PS into the inner channel of TMV via electrostatic interactions increases reagent delivery (Lee, Carpenter, Wen, Ghiladi, & Steinmetz, 2016). PS/vehicle systems for PDT have been described using CCMV encapsulation of a water-soluble phthalocyanine (Pc) and packing of Zn-EpPor in CPMV (Wen et al., 2016) and Physalis Mottle VLPs (Masarapu et al., 2017). (Brasch et al., 2011).

4.1.8 MRI contrast agent loading

Contrast compounds are often used in MRI (Bruckman, Yu, & Steinmetz, 2013). As T2-weighted contrast agents, rod-shaped and spherical PVNPs loaded with contrast agents by conjugating Gd-DOTA to lysines on PVX (Duc HT Le, Hu, Commandeur, & Steinmetz, 2017), self-assembly of the capsid protein of BMV around iron oxide nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄), and gold-coated iron oxide nanoparticles (-Fe₂O₃@Au PV As a bimodal contrast agent, a bimodal contrast agent was produced by loading dysprosium (Dy³⁺) and the dye Cy7.5 in the internal cavity of TMV and targeting integrin 2 1 with an Asp-Gly-Glu-Ala (DGEA) peptide through a polyethylene glycol linker on the exterior capsid surface (Hu et al., 2017). When paramagnetic organic radical contrast agents are conjugated to the surface of TMV, they exhibit value for T1 and T2 contrast (Dharmarwardana et al., 2018). For loading imaging agents, nanoassembly and bioconjugation are typical approaches.

4.1.9 Metal materials loading

A suitable structural and chemical model is necessary for bio-mineralization, and PVNPs can provide these qualities. They are adaptable substrates for the production of tiny, thin metal and metal oxide mineral formations. Metals such as Ag, Ni, Co, Cu, Pt, Co-Pt, and Fe-Pt may be deposited into the central core of TMV for catalysis and sensing, and metals such as Ag, Ni, Co, Cu, Pt, Co-Pt, and Fe-Pt may be deposited into the central core of TMV for catalysis and sensing (Culver et al., 2015; M. Kobayashi, Seki, Tabata, Watanabe, & Yamashita, 2010). Surface modification of CPMV using cationic polyelectrolyte allows for

the adsorption of anionic gold complexes, which are subsequently readily reduced to create a metallic gold coating under moderate conditions (A. A. Aljabali, Lomonosoff, & Evans, 2011).

4.2 PVNPs loaded with cargoes have applications.

PVNPs' loading tactics and features combine to make them a flexible biological platform for a wide range of applications. They provide platforms with broad applications in energy transfer via metal mineralization (Thangavelu et al., 2018), light-harvesting systems via chromophore couplings (Delor et al., 2018), sensing via thousands of identical receptor peptides (Zang, Gerasopoulos, Brown, Culver, & Ghodssi, 2017), nanoreactors/biocatalysts via encapsulation of catalase (P. L. Chariou, Doga, et al., 2019; P. L. Chariou, Wang, et al., 2019; Chariou & Steinmetz, 2017). Therapeutic delivery, bioimaging, vaccine development, immunotherapy, and tissue engineering are some of the medical applications for PVNPs (Wang & Steinmetz, 2019). (T. Liu et al., 2019). Theranostic reagents, which include both therapeutic and imaging reagents on the same platform, have a lot of promise thanks to the variety of cargo loading (Beatty & Lewis, 2019).

PVNP modifications for in vivo interventions

PVNPs are excellent nanoscaffolds for polyvalent display of various functional groups by genetic and chemical changes, allowing in vivo interventions to be influenced (Kaur, Valarmathi, Potts, & Wang, 2008; Raja et al., 2019). Despite their many benefits, PVNPs' in vivo use is restricted by off-target distribution, short circulation duration, plasma protein coronas, and immune system clearance (Chariou et al., 2015; K. Kobayashi, Wei, Iida, Ijiro, & Niikura, 2014; Lee et al., 2015; A. S. Pitek, Wen, Shukla, & Steinmetz, 2016; S. Shukla, Eber, et al., 2015). PVNPs can be changed in form, as well as having targeted ligands and polymer coatings added to them, to overcome these restrictions. PEGylation and a high aspect ratio of PVNPs, for example, increase circulation duration and limit absorption by phagocytic cells, which is important for increased tumor homing and tissue penetration. Furthermore, adding ligands that bind to receptors overexpressed on certain cell types genetically or chemically can improve cell specificity (P. L. Chariou, Doga, et al., 2019; P. L. Chariou, Wang, et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2016; Röder et al., 2019).

5.1 Improving tissue engineering by modifying PVNP

PVNPs can be changed into compounds that have affinity for certain cell markers, such as RGD, peptides, or protein ligands, to aid in tissue engineering. PVNPs and mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), for example, interact to promote cell proliferation and differentiation (J. Luckanagul et al., 2012). PVNPs modified with RGD peptides aid NP escape from the vasculature and boost MSC proliferation and osteogenic differentiation by boosting the expression of osteo-specific markers (e.g., osteocalcin, bone morphogenetic protein 2; Metavarayuth et al., 2019). The hydroxyapatite crystal nucleation required for bone marrow-derived MSC development for better bone tissue replacement is also provided by this platform (Lauria et al., 2017; J. A. Luckanagul, Lee, You, Yang, & Wang, 2015; Sitasuwan, Lee, Li, Nguyen, & Wang, 2014). Furthermore, particle deposition at the site of vascular injury was seen with CPMV and TMV modified with fibrin-binding peptides such as CREKA and GPRPP, which facilitated injured tissue regeneration (Wen, Wang, et al., 2015).

5.2 Improving vaccines by modifying PVNP

PVNPs are possibilities for vaccines and immunotherapy because they include vaccine or tumor antigens. A PVNP-based vaccination for Rift Valley Fever Virus is a safe, quick-to-

produce, and scalable alternative to previous vaccination alternatives. PVNPs are used in vaccine development in two ways: as a nanoscaffold for delivering the epitope and as an adjuvant to boost the immune response. The immunogenicity of distinct epitopes on CPMV, TMV, and PVX, for example, was investigated for bacteria and virus-related disorders (Meshcheryakova et al., 2009; Sahithi et al., 2019). PVNP-based cancer vaccines, such as PVX, CCMV, CPMV, and SeMV, have recently been produced by showing HER2 epitopes to induce protection against HER2+ cancers (Cai et al., 2019; S. Shukla et al., 2017). Some PVNPs, such as CPMV, have a natural immunogenicity and can be used as adjuvants in vaccines. This is very beneficial for cancer treatment with in situ vaccination (A. E. Czapar, Tiu, Veliz, Pokorski, & Steinmetz, 2018; Lebel et al., 2016; Lizotte et al., 2016).

5.3 Improving freight delivery by modifying PVNP

The payload should be packaged and delivered to the relevant sites, cells, and subcellular locations in target cells using a PVNP-based nanocarrier. PVNP has been produced as a carrier of medications (e.g., MTX) for chemotherapy (Lam et al., 2018), gold, and ruthenium for photothermal treatment (P. L. Chariou, Doga, et al., 2019), porphyrin-based PS medicines (Zn-Por) for PDT (P. L. Chariou, Wang, et al., 2019), and contrast agents for bioimaging. For example, in cancer therapy, nontargeted PVNP formulations might concentrate in the tumor microenvironment due to shape and size, as well as the occasionally leaky vasculature of the tumor tissue, in a highly variable process known as increased permeability and retention (Sandra, Khaliq, Sunna, & Care, 2019). Because many NP are quickly swallowed by phagocytes, it is a passive and nonspecific method that may be ineffectual (Koudelka et al., 2015). As a result, altering the surface or form to conceal them from the immune system might prolong circulation time and boost target tissue accumulation (Lee et al., 2015). (P. L. Chariou, Doga, et al., 2019; P. L. Chariou, Wang, et al., 2019; D. H. T. Le et al., 2018; X. Liu, Wu, et al., 2016). Elongated PVNPs with a high aspect ratio exhibit faster tissue diffusion rates than spherical particles, according to recent research (Röder et al., 2019).

Targeting ligands that bind to specific molecular receptors can be employed to increase accumulation in target tissues. Folic acid (FA) (Alemzadeh et al., 2019), S100A9 peptide (Park et al., 2019), TRAIL (D. H. T. Le, Commandeur, & Steinmetz, 2019), and transferrin (D. H. T. Le, Commandeur, & Steinmetz, 2019) are all examples (Chariou et al., 2015; S. Shukla, DiFranco, Wen, Commandeur, & Steinmetz, 2015). FA, a cancer-cell-targeting ligand, was conjugated to the Hibiscus chlorotic ringspot virus, which resulted in cancer cell tropism (Ren, Wong, & Lim, 2010). A promising theranostic approach that can be used to facilitate photothermal therapy and imaging is Gd-loaded TMV coated with the mussel-inspired biopolymer polydopamine (Hu, Yang, et al., 2019) and human serum albumin (A. Pitek, Hu, Shukla, & Steinmetz, 2018) or TRAIL for killing tumor cells (D. H. T. Le et al., 2019).

4. Conclusion

PVNPs can be employed in biological systems to load and transport cargo. Small dimensions, high avidity target binding owing to several targeting ligands per PVNP, customizable and modular physicochemical features, capacity for multiplexing for imaging, and the accompanying possibility for large payload delivery in various settings are all factors that contribute to their utility. The creation of highly functional materials for future uses is possible because of physicochemical and genetic modification. PVNPs can be tailored and loaded for specific applications using (a) physical techniques that allow cargo to be loaded via physical interactions; (b) chemical techniques that link cargo or targeting ligands to the

exterior or interior capsid; (c) genetic techniques that allow for precise and repeatable manipulations; and (d) combined techniques that combine multiple loading methods to generate more options. To maximize loading, it is critical to select the most effective approaches to couple with a suitable cargo. The loading and release of cargo from within the particle are important features of PVNP-based delivery systems, and both processes are frequently linked. The features of the PVNP, the cargo to be loaded, and the reason for creating the specific nanoparticle all influence which approaches are best for a given system.

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